

Psychiatry as a Career Choice

Amna Awais¹, Neha Nadeem¹, Muhammad Kashif Mehmood¹, Ayesha Younus²

¹ Students of Final Year MBBS, RMU

² Assistant Professor, Department of Psychiatry, BBH

Abstract

Background: To determine frequency of students in Rawalpindi Medical University who would opt for psychiatry as their future career. Along with that we will determine the reasons which encourage or discourage students from choosing Psychiatry.

Subjects and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted at Rawalpindi Medical University, including MBBS students of the five academic years. All study participants were given a semi-structured questionnaire. The data was entered and analyzed using SPSS version 22 and all categorical variables were expressed both as frequencies and percentages.

Results: Psychiatry was the third most common career choice (10.2%) following Surgery (31.8%) and Medicine (26%). However, trend of opting for Psychiatry as a career specialty declined with the advancing academic years. Majority of the respondents who were in favor of Psychiatry had a rural background and belonged to a high socio economic group. Females (11.1%) were slightly more inclined towards this specialty compared to their males (7.8%). Among the reasons for choosing Psychiatry as career specialty, the most common ones were "need to help people with mental illness" (89.8%), "need for more Psychiatrists in Pakistan" (89.1%) and "interest in the subject" (89.9%). Most frequently opted reasons for not choosing this field were "don't suit my temperament (68.4%)", "can negatively affect my mental health" (43.1%) and "work is not clinical enough" (42.7%).

Conclusion: Students showed a stronger inclination towards psychiatry as compared to their peers in most countries worldwide. However, the popularity of Psychiatry as a career choice declined as the academic years progressed. This could be attributed to a variety of factors including experiencing clinical rotations in Psychiatry during the undergraduate program and poor understanding of the pathophysiology of psychiatric diseases.

Key Words: Student, career choice, psychiatry, specialty

Introduction

Mental health is an important part of health. Mental disorders have an impact on an individual as well as on national productivity¹. In the most recent WHO burden of disease study mental, neurological and substance abuse accounts for 10.4% of global disability adjusted life years (DALYs) and 28.5% of global years lived with disability (YLDs)². A study conducted in rural Pakistan stated that out of 664 people, 66% women and 25% men showed signs of mental disorders, with a direct relationship with poverty.³ About 0.4% is being allocated to mental health out of the total health care budget.⁴ Whereas in Pakistan there are only 0.002 psychiatrists per 100000 population.⁵

A number of researches have been done across the globe to find out medical students' interest in psychiatry. In USA, Psychiatry was rated lower than other specialties with regard to job satisfaction, financial reward, enjoyable work etc. ⁶. In the UK, medical students considered psychiatry as non-choice option for their career.⁷ Chinese medical students also showed a negative attitude towards psychiatry as a career, especially with respect to financial reward and prestige.⁸ In India, majority of medical interns did not favor psychiatry as a career choice.⁹ A study conducted in Lahore revealed that psychiatry was third least preferred speciality.¹⁰ In Karachi, medical students showed positive perception about Psychiatry as a subject. However, majority were reluctant to choose Psychiatry as a career.¹¹

This will be the first documented study of its kind being conducted at Rawalpindi medical university. In addition to determining the frequency of medical students opting for psychiatry, we intend to determine the reasons for their choice as well.

Pakistan faces a staggering burden of psychiatric illness. On average 4.15 psychiatrists are

recommended per 100,000 population by WHO. Where as in Pakistan, the number of psychiatrists per 100,000 population is 0.002. We wish to highlight and address the reasons why medical students are reluctant to opt for this profession, in order to better combat the burden of psychiatric morbidity. Our research will generate data that will be of profound importance in planning educational and awareness programs, and to provide adequate healthcare to the public.

Materials & Methods

This cross-sectional study was undertaken in Rawalpindi Medical University (new teaching block and old campus) after approval from Institutional Research Forum of RMU. The study population comprised of medical students from each of the five academic years of RMU. WHO sample size calculator was used to calculate the minimally required sample size. Keeping level of confidence 95%, anticipated population proportion 45%¹¹, absolute precision 5%, sample size came out to be 381. Our study population comprised of medical students of RMU from the each of the five academic years. The sampling technique used was stratified random sampling, based on gender and academic year. We randomly chose equal number of students from each of the five academic years. After informed verbal consent of selected students, a semi structured questionnaire was administered. First section of the questionnaire dealt with the demographic details (age, gender, academic year, boarding status, residence, and monthly family income), career preferences and reason for choosing the particular specialty. In the second section of the Performa, a question regarding choosing psychiatry as a career was asked separately. Along with that there were 17 statements regarding the possible reasons for choosing and not choosing psychiatry. With each statement three options of agree, disagree and neutral were given. Students filled the questionnaire with their free will. The data was entered and analyzed by SPSS version 22. For all variables, frequencies and percentages were calculated.

Results

A total of 381 students participated in the study. Number of female students in the sample was more than male students owing to the greater population of females in our university. Mean age of the

respondents was 20 years (SD=1.68). Table I summarizes the demographic characteristics of the students.

Table I. Demographic Characteristics Of Medical Students (n=381)

GENDER	NUMBER(n)	PERCENTAGE
• Male	102	26.8%
• Female	279	73.2%
RESIDENCE		
• Rural	36	9.4%
• Urban	345	90.6%
BOARDING STATUS		
• Boarder	126	33.1%
• Non-boarder	254	66.7%
MONTHLY FAMILY INCOME(Rs)		
• Less than 50,000	42	11%
• 50,000 to 100,000	157	41.2%
• More than 100,000	180	47.2%

Figure I gives us the career choices of medical students from all five years. Other fields included oncology (n=7), dermatology (n=9), radiology (n=4), eye (n=2), ENT (n=1), neurology (n=2), pathology (n=3), microbiology (n=1), rheumatology (n=2), and community medicine (n=1).

Fig.I: Career choices of Medical Students (n=381)

Majority of the cases who selected surgery, medicine , paediatrics and gynae/obs stated that it was their subject of interest; there is well understood pathophysiology of disease and clear cut treatments; patients have high cure rates. While students who selected psychiatry stated that it is their subject of interest and there is need for greater number of professionals in this field in Pakistan/overseas. Highest percentage of students who considered psychiatry as top choice for their career was from first year. More females were in favor of Psychiatry compared to males in all years. Reasons for choosing and not choosing Psychiatry as career specialty are shown in figures II and III.

Fig IIA: Reasons for Choosing Psychiatry

Fig IIB: Reasons For Choosing Psychiatry

Fig.IIIA: Reasons For Not Choosing Psychiatry

Fig.IIIB: Reasons For Not Choosing Psychiatry

Discussion

The aim of the research was to determine the percentage of students who would opt for psychiatry as a career in RMU. Along with that we intended to

explore the reasons which encouraged or discouraged students from pursuing this specialty.

Our study revealed that after Surgery and Medicine, psychiatry was the most commonly preferred specialty. Surprisingly, Obstetrics/Gynecology and pediatrics were found less attractive than psychiatry. This is similar to the results of the study conducted in China⁸, Serbia²² and US⁶, where surgery and medicine were the most commonly opted for fields. However, Gynecology/Obstetrics and Pediatrics were more popular than psychiatry in the US and China. In the UK⁷, Surgery, Pediatrics and General Practice were the leading career choices, understandably because of the highly paid job setups and Psychiatry and Gynecology/Obstetrics were least preferred. In our study, 10.2% students ranked it as top choice for their future career, compared to 1.6% in China and 0.5% in USA. 24.2% were considering it as a possible choice, which contrasts a percentage of 7.2 in the US.

Our results are similar to a study done in Serbia, where students ranked surgery, medicine and pediatrics as their top choice followed by psychiatry²². Gynecology was less attractive than psychiatry.

We compared our results with local researches as well. According to a research conducted in three medical colleges of Karachi, the percentage of students willing to choose psychiatry as a career were 37%, 45% and 30%¹¹. This study is consistent with ours that more students are beginning to take interest in psychiatry as a career. This can be explained by the fact, as highlighted by the results of our study, that students find Psychiatry intriguing as a subject and realize the deficit of Psychiatric professionals in the country, and they feel that the Psychiatric illnesses are not being properly addressed.

Another recent study which included third year medical students from four medical colleges in different regions of Pakistan showed that 7.6% students considered psychiatry as chosen career or a highly likely choice.¹⁷ This is more comparable to our results than to the international results.

These local researches show that in Pakistan there is definitely a positive trend of choosing Psychiatry as a specialty.

Perceptions of psychiatry vary from region to region, as indicated by a comparison study between US and Spanish medical students.²¹ Spanish students showed a more positive attitude towards psychiatry and this was reflected in the fact that more Spanish students (6%) opted for psychiatry compared to US students

(4.5%) This may be attributed to varying socioeconomic and cultural factors.

Another aspect that was unraveled in our study was that females were more inclined towards psychiatry as compared to their male counterparts. This is consistent with previous studies.¹⁸ This can be explained by the fact that Psychiatric calls are less demanding with regards to time and physical effort, especially considering the social and domestic obligations the females in South East Asia are expected to fulfill.

We found that the most important reason for pursuing this specialty was the desire to help people with mental health issues which are on the rise, as stated in the Human Right Commission of Pakistan (HRCP) report revealing that 34% of Pakistan's population is suffering from some form of mental illness. Students realize the need for more psychiatrists in Pakistan. Psychiatrist to patient ratio is unbalanced; 1 psychiatrist has to see 115000 patients of depression, 8000 patients of bipolar disorders, 4000 patients of substance abuse. These results are consistent with a study conducted on Iranian residents of Psychiatry¹⁹.

The next important factor was interest in the subject. This can be attributed to the working of the human mind and behavior, which is still not fully understood and intrigues even an individual who hasn't yet experience clinical rotations in Psychiatry. This also explains why many of the first year students in our Study had chosen this option for their choice. In Serbia these factors were the top influencers²² in medical students for their choice.

Personal or family experience of a mental problem was positively associated with choosing psychiatry in our study and this factor is similar to some other studies.^{7,20} However among Iranian residents, this factor had a negative effect on their choice of psychiatry.¹⁹ Experience of a mental problem tends to make an individual more empathetic towards psychiatric patients and influences them to help them.

Students showed neutral response to the statement that jobs in psychiatry would be easy to find. This can be because of the small percentage of psychiatrics in our country and the consequent low probability of an average student having personally known a psychiatrist, and also to the brief psychiatric clinical rotations in our undergraduate programs.

Most common reason for not choosing psychiatry was that Psychiatry did not suit their temperament.

Individuals from our sample pool had different interpretations of 'temperament', ranging from "it's an abstract subject" to "I don't have the communication skills" and "it's difficult to take a good history" and "It's distressing and boring" and "you can't perform any clinical tests or investigations to reach diagnosis". In the UK⁷ too, students found psychiatry 'boring', 'depressing' and 'frustrating'. All these reasons fell under the same factor, contributing to its high percentage.

Around 40% students feared that interacting with psychiatric patients would have negative impact on their mental health and there could be risk of assault. This trend aligns with research done in USA and Serbia.^{6,22} Psychiatric patients are generally unpredictable in behavior and this can physically lash onto the Psychiatrist.

Majority of the students were of the opinion that work in Psychiatry is not clinical enough and they were not sure regarding the effectiveness of the treatment in the psychiatric patients. However, these were major aversion factors in the study of USA back in 1990⁶. This may be due to students 'poor knowledge about newer antidepressants, mood stabilizers, atypical anti psychotics which have revolutionized the pharmacological treatment of mental illness. Secondly, in our country research work is inadequate and psychiatric patients are not thoroughly studied to find out the cause behind their mental health disturbance.

Regarding the aspect of psychiatry's poor public image, students had mixed views. 35% Students agreed, 31% disagreed, and 33% were neutral. While students disagreed with the view that psychiatrists are disrespected by doctors in other fields. This is in opposition with the study conducted on UK graduates who initially chose psychiatry but didn't pursue it as a long term career. The major reasons cited were poor image of psychiatry in society and lack of respect granted to psychiatrists by their peers.²³

Similarly low financial reward in psychiatry was not an important discouraging factor in our study but it had a negative effect on choosing psychiatry among Iranian residents.¹⁹ These differences are because of the fact that the studies of the UK and Iran were done on the psychiatric residents who were having personal experience in the field while our respondents were undergraduate students who had not yet entered the field.

Career preferences as stated by students in the early years of training are liable to change after they

graduate as they are exposed to different clinical rotations. This is one limitation in our study. 17% of first year students and only 7% of final year students opted for psychiatry. Final year students, for their medical career, ranked Medicine as first choice, Surgery as second, pediatrics as third, followed by other fields which included dermatology and oncology mostly and then Psychiatry. This trend is completely different from the overall result of all five academic years about career preferences in our study.

Conclusion

Students expressed a stronger affinity for psychiatry when compared to their peers in most countries worldwide. However, the popularity of Psychiatry declined as the academic years progressed. This may be due to the brief period of psychiatric clinical rotations in our university. Students get little knowledge about different varieties of psychiatric disorders, their treatments and prognosis. Exposure to the field would clear students' concepts regarding clinical work in psychiatry and management of psychiatric patients and illnesses. Students who expressed their interest in the subject, and aimed to help people with mental illnesses and intended to overcome the deficiency of psychiatrist should be properly counseled so that they don't lose their interest. 10.2% students' top choice was psychiatry and 24.2% were considering choosing it. These significant percentages are higher still among students of Karachi.¹¹ With proper direction and improvement of teaching programs, these students can help bridge the psychiatrist-patient ratio in our country.

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